

Correlation of Parent's Concern Towards Their Child's Oral Health, Considering Caries Index.

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Abstract—

Introduction

Oral hygiene plays a crucial role in preventing dental caries and periodontal diseases which when left untreated result in pain, and premature tooth loss.

Aim

This study is aimed to assess the parental knowledge about their child's oral health and to assess the oral health status of children and to analyze its association with the education level of their parents.

Materials and Methods

This is a cross-sectional study conducted on 50 patients. Data was collected using a questionnaire and analyzed using STATA version 10.1, 2011 and overall comparison of means across the groups was performed using ANOVA (F-test).

Results

Among the 41 children, 19.51% (8 children) had deciduous (primary) dentition, that is, 6 years. 60.98% (25 children) had mixed dentition that is 7-11 years and 19.51% (8 children) had permanent dentition that is, 12-14 years. The results clearly indicate that there is no correlation of mean DMFT scores with the parent's occupation. The parental concern is purely based upon the knowledge of child's oral health.

Conclusion

Parents have less concern towards their child's oral health considering their caries index. Thus, there is need of imparting knowledge through various awareness programs or by the means of other social media resources to the parents.

Keywords— Oral health, parental concern, dental caries, children, parental awareness

INTRODUCTION

Oral hygiene has an important role in preventing dental caries and periodontal diseases. This problem is frequently marginalized or even ignored by parents/guardians, what affects child's whole further life. The purpose of this study is to create awareness among parents regarding the consequences of caries and how important is regular dental check-up. These diseases when left untreated can result in pain, emergency visits, premature tooth loss with its sequel of compromised chewing and harm to the permanent dentition in young children ¹. Also, dental caries is an important global health problem and its prevalence is still high, particularly in children. It is the main reason for tooth loss and oral pain.

Dental caries is not self-limiting and without proper care can spread and destroy the entire tooth structure, but if treated within time can be arrested and the tooth can be restored. Young children are not capable of brushing their own teeth properly; therefore, it is the parent's responsibility to take care of their child's oral hygiene. ² As a result, parental awareness of their children's dental needs (i.e. cleaning status) may have an important role in preventing future oral health problems. ³ Parental involvement has a significant role in children's oral hygiene practices. However, a high percentage of parents do not adequately pay attention to their child's oral hygiene and overestimate the quality of cleaning behavior when it is performed by children themselves. ⁴

The reason I chose this study is that parents nowadays tend to ignore their child's oral health, and they feel that it is not important to treat the primary teeth as they will exfoliate and will be replaced by the permanent teeth. Also, even if they notice caries, they think it is unnecessary to treat it unless it is associated with pain and so the entire tooth is decayed, and it may hamper the growth of underlying permanent teeth.

In developing countries, poor eating habits, easy access to refined carbohydrates, irregular brushing habits and use of low fluoridated toothpastes also contribute to dental caries. So it is very important that parents should be aware of their child's oral health. Poor oral health of child is often due to poor attitude of parents. It also leads to missed school hours, toothache and several impairments in daily activities of children. Parents awareness will not only help them recognize their child's dental needs, but also improve the oral hygiene status of children. It will also promote good health of coming permanent teeth and help in good oral health.

The advantages of this study are:

1. Parents will be aware and well-versed about their child's dental needs.
2. Promote good oral health.
3. Prevention of any oral pain related to caries.
4. It will prevent the tooth loss and somehow boost the confidence of the child.

This study is a questionnaire-based study in which parents were asked to fill the general questions regarding their child's oral health. The oral cavity of the child was examined and correlated with parents' answers. This helped the parents to know where they are lacking and how much knowledge they need to gain. They also came to know about certain things that they previously were unaware of, and also thought it's important for their child to brush their teeth twice daily.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

In this study, caries index among 6-14 years old children were assessed. Due to lack of awareness of parents, there might be poor oral hygiene practices among these children. Hence, there is a need to spread awareness about the proper oral hygiene practices. Therefore, in this study firstly DMFT score was assessed, and then the parents were made aware about the importance of dental check-ups and treatment of primary dentition and also proper oral hygiene maintenance in children.

S. Shaghaghian et al. (2016) ³ performed a questionnaire-based study which collected the information on parental awareness about their child's oral health & hygiene, parents of children aged 3 to 6 years old at Shiraz, Southern Iran were a part of this study.

In their study, it was concluded that many parents in Shiraz were not aware of their child's oral hygiene status. The aware parents had higher education level and socioeconomic status and their children had better oral health status. Also, their children had better oral hygiene and less dental caries. A majority of the low-educated parents were unaware of their child's unclean/unhygienic dental status. Hence, in the study, they also concluded that educational interventions are recommended to improve parental awareness regarding their child's oral hygiene. Moreover, there is a need to spread awareness among the parents so that they get to know about proper methods of tooth brushing and other home preventive measures, irrespective of the parents' education status.

Priyanka Achalu et al. (2019) ⁷ performed a study by following qualitative methodology. The study was about child nutrition and oral health practices, which included 102 mothers in eight rural Salvadoran communities in El Salvador. On average, mothers were 30-31 years of age with low income. This study identified three major themes hierarchical - based changes, mothers' knowledge and practices, and access and obstacles to items and services-with nutrition and oral health problems for each major theme.

This study concluded that the mothers/caregivers had basic knowledge regarding the children's nutrition and oral health. However, they faced a substantial amount of obstacles to apply their knowledge-primarily the widespread sale of cheap, non-nutritious snacks and beverages with high sugar content in and around schools, and the peer or social pressure to give money to their children to buy treats daily. In addition, they faced major obstacles to access dental services for their children and barriers like distance, transportation, and cost of dental services.

Even when there is proper awareness among the mothers about dental hygiene & health, they should be educated about the adverse effects of processed, non-nutritious snacks and beverages with high sugar content and also proper oral hygiene practices. The mothers should also be made aware that their child's health is their top-most responsibility, hence they should not give money to their children to buy cheap, non-nutritious snacks and sugary beverages under social or peer-pressure. There should also be easy access to dental care facilities for children in and around schools.

Elham Bozorgmehr et al. (2013) ⁶ did an interventional study about relationship between oral health behavior of parents and oral health status and behavior of their children in preschool children in Kerman, South East of Iran.

In this study, over 5 years old children and their parents were enrolled. Selection of schools was by clustering method from the list of 160 elementary schools in Kerman, and 22 children randomly enrolled from each school with their parents into the study.

In the study, it was concluded that some important health behaviors in parents, such as tooth brushing habits and frequency of consumption of sweet foods, are important determinants of the same behaviors in their young children. Children with high-educated parents had lower plaque index than the others. As children tend to mirror the behavior & habits of their elders ⁷ people they are surrounded by, promoting parents' knowledge, attitude & behavior regarding their oral hygiene could play a major role & affect their children oral health, behavior, habits & hence improve their dental health.

Deepa Gurunathan et al. (2018) ⁷ performed a questionnaire-based study to evaluate the influence of parental education on knowledge, attitude, and practice of mothers regarding oral health of primary school children in Chennai.

The study concluded that the mothers who have only studied till high school, are not much aware of the preventive practices measures of dental diseases, importance of tooth brushing, and dental visits. Therefore, it is the responsibility of the government and health care providers to convey or impart oral health knowledge to mothers, as they are the first role-models for most of the children.

Francesca Calcagnile et al. (2019) ⁸ performed a questionnaire-based study to evaluate the knowledge and awareness of parents about potential oral health risk factors and correct management of oral hygiene of their preschool children. It included parents of 3-5year aged children in Campobasso, Italy.

From this survey, it was concluded that solely by the parents' knowledge, it reflects that parents are not fully trained and informed about the management & care of their child's oral hygiene. Hence, it is necessary to promote a parental oral health awareness program since beginning of the children's school, to control their oral health risk status.

Fernanda Alves de Lima Della Libera Trindade et al. (2015)⁹ performed an observational cross-sectional study to evaluate the knowledge of parents and guardians of school-going children about oral hygiene and diet in a shelter and in a higher education institution. This was conducted in Rio de Janeiro, Brazil and included 82 guardians of children aged 0-12 years.

The study concluded that parents and guardians of children at Teresa of Jesus Shelter had more knowledge about oral hygiene and diet than respondents of Veiga de Almeida University despite the terrible socio-economic conditions, at Teresa of Jesus Shelter. Also, implying that knowledge about oral hygiene & health in children is sometimes independent of the socio-economic conditions of parents and guardians.

Fatima Ashkanani et al. (2013)¹⁰ performed a cross-sectional study to assess the knowledge, attitudes and practices of caregivers in Kuwait in relation to the oral health of preschool children. A total number of 334 caregivers were a part of this study

The study concluded that the caregivers had weak knowledge and practice about the oral health of preschool children. They also suggested that there was strong need to address infants' oral health-related issues. Therefore, the caregivers should be educated & well-informed about the oral health & hygiene in children.

Suresh BS et al. (2010)¹¹ performed a study to assess the mothers' knowledge about the oral health of their pre-school children in Moradabad, India. This included mothers of children aged 1-4 years, attending the hospital for vaccination or regular check-ups.

The study concluded that mothers had only insufficient or partial knowledge about oral health of children. Majority of the mothers had insufficient knowledge about the fact that sharing of utensils can transmit bacteria called *S. mutans* which causes caries in children. Hence, the doctors or medical personnel, who are the first to come in contact with expectant and new mothers, need to provide proper and precise information about oral health care for infants.

Deepika Yadav et al. (2022)¹² performed a cross-sectional study to report caregivers' oral health and early childhood caries (ECC) knowledge and attitude towards preschool children attending Anganwadi centers in Mysuru. This study included 377 children and their caregivers.

The study concluded that the caregivers of the preschool children were aware & had a good amount of knowledge about the importance of oral health. Even though caregivers had a strong knowledge & awareness of oral health, they lacked in understanding of the importance of feeding patterns in early childhood caries. They preferred to leave deciduous carious teeth

alone because they fall out anyway, implying a lack of understanding of the importance of deciduous carious teeth.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

Aim of the study-

This study targets the evaluation of parental awareness in relation to the dental health of their children.

Primary objective –

- Parental knowledge about their child's oral health.
- To assess the oral health status of children and to analyze its association with the education level of their parents.

Secondary objective –

- To assess the caries index (DMFT) among 6-14 years old children.
- To identify the parents' first dental visit.
- To assess parents' knowledge related to dental problems among children
- To demonstrate parents' source of dental health information.
- To compare if there is a statistically significant difference between parents' type, educational level, occupation, and the overall knowledge related to oral health.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study design

This is a cross-sectional study in which a pretested self-designed questionnaire was used to collect information from parents of 50 children that reported in college in Nagpur district. Statistical analysis was done, and Pierson Chi-square test was used.

Type of study

This is a questionnaire-based study.

Study site

This study was conducted in the Department of Pedodontics and Preventive Dentistry, in present college in Nagpur district.

Duration of study

This study was carried out from August 2022 to September 2022.

Number of subject/ samples that were used

The number of subjects used to carry out the study was 41 children aged 6-14 years.

Inclusion / exclusion criteria

Inclusion criteria:

- Age between 6-14 years.
- Patients who have given consent for study.

Exclusion criteria:

- Mentally retarded patients.
- Congenital anomalies.

Withdrawal criteria:

- Patient who is not ready for consent.
- Non-cooperative.

Data collection tools

- Diagnostic instruments: mouth mirror, probe, tweezers
- PPE Kit
- Detailed case history

Data collection methods

The data were collected based on a pretested questionnaire including general characteristics (age and gender of child), occupation of parent, education status of parent, oral hygiene habits, dental check-ups importance of treatment of caries, etc. was filled by face-to-face interview by the parents of 6-14 year old children.

Questionnaire

The questionnaire consisted of 11 questions concerning parental and their children's oral health behavior and parental attitudes toward dental caries in their children were also included, seeking to investigate how parental attitudes may impact their child's behaviors. The questionnaire was framed in two languages; one in English and one in the regional language, that is, Marathi. The parents, who could read the forms, filled it on their own. A questionnaire

was filled for those parents who could not read the forms on their own by explaining the questions to them, and then their answers were marked on the forms.

CHILD'S ORAL HEALTH AWARENESS
QUESTIONNAIRE FOR PARENTS

AGE OF THE CHILD: _____

GENDER OF CHILD: _____

OCCUPATION OF PARENT: _____

EDUCATION STATUS OF PARENT: _____

1) Do you think that regular dental check-up is important? YES NO

2) Has your child been to the dentist before? YES NO

3) Does your child brush his/her teeth twice a day? YES NO

4) Is your child's toothpaste fluoridated? YES NO

5) Does your child use mouthwash to rinse mouth? YES NO

6) Does your child have caries? YES NO

7) Do you think caries are harmful? YES NO

8) Do you feel that it is important to treat caries? YES NO

9) Has your child suffered from oral pain before? YES NO

10) Do you think it is important to visit dentist if you notice caries that are asymptomatic? YES NO

11) Do you know the eruption and exfoliation stage of teeth? YES NO

Figure 1: Questionnaire (English)

प्रश्नावली

मुलाचे वय: _____

मुलाचे लिंग: _____

पालकांचा व्यवसाय: _____

पालकांची शैक्षणिक स्थिती: _____

१) दातांचे नियमित तपासणी करणे महत्वाचे आहे असे तुम्हाला वाटते का?	होय	नाही
२) तुमचे मुलं यापूर्वी दन्तवैद्य कडे गेले आहेत का?	होय	नाही
३) तुमचे मुलं दिवसातून दोन दा दात घासतात का?	होय	नाही
४) तुमच्या मुलाची टूथपेस्ट फ्ल्युओरीडेटेड आहे का?	होय	नाही
५) तुमचे मुलं तोंड धुण्यासाठी मौथवॉश वापरतात का?	होय	नाही
६) तुमच्या मुलाला दातात कीड आहे का?	होय	नाही
७) दातांची कीड हानिकारक आहेत असे तुम्हाला वाटते का?	होय	नाही
८) तुम्हाला दातांच्या कीड चे उपचार करणे महत्वाचे वाटते का?	होय	नाही
९) तुमच्या मुलाला या आधी तोंडी वेदना झाल्या आहेत का?	होय	नाही
१०) तुम्हाला लक्षणे नसलेले कीड दिसल्यास दंतवैद्याला भेट देणे महत्वाचे आहे असे वाटते का?	होय	नाही
११) तुम्हाला दुधाच्या दाताचा इरपशन आणि एक्सफॉलिएशन स्टेज माहिती आहे का?	होय	नाही

Figure 2: Questionnaire (Marathi)

Informed consent procedures

Informed consent was taken from the parents before initiation of the study.

Sample collection

Random sampling method

Statistical tests used for data analysis

The statistical analysis was applied by employing the statistical software STATA version 10.1, 2011, where both Descriptive and Inferential Statistics procedures were used, these different

statistical tools involved; summarized responses and qualitative variables with frequencies and percentage. Inferential statistics included P-values from hypothesis testing procedures. Overall comparison of means across the groups was performed using ANOVA (F-test).

Quantitative variables are summarized with mean and standardization.

Association between parents' demographics with oral health status of the child is evaluated by Pierson's Chi-square test.

A P-value less than 0.05 will be considered statistically significant for all the comparisons.

Ethical Consent

All ethical issues were considered during the process of this study and the proposal was approved by the Institutional Ethical Committee of respective college where the study was conducted, and the consent form was filled by participants before starting the study.

INFORM CONSENT FORM
Reference ID : 2022-12060
Topic: Correlation of parents concern towards their child's oral health considering caries index.
I Mr./Mrs. of Age years
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• I am willing to participate in this study entitled "Correlation of parents concern towards their child's oral health considering caries index."
I am willing to give all the information needed for the study when required. All the procedure, objectives and nature of study have been explained to me in detail in my own vernacular language. Hence, I am giving this written consent after full understanding of the study.
Signature of the subject
I hereby declare that I have informed the detailed procedure and objective of the study to the patient in their own vernacular language.
Signature of Principal Investigator

Figure 3: Informed Consent Form

Figure 4: IEC Certificate

Clinical oral examination

The patient's oral health was assessed with the help of an artificial light source, mouth mirror, a WHO periodontal probe and disposable gloves and masks while they were sitting on a chair in a comfortable position. The oral health examination in each child included DMFT for assessment of dental caries.

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

Observations

Categories	Frequency
Business	9
Employee	14
Homemaker	4
Labor	14

Table 1: Categories vs Frequency

Figure 5: Categories vs Frequency pie chart

A total of 41 children were part of this study. Categorization of the parents was done by their occupations. Amongst these, 22% (9 people) were businessman, 34% (14 people) were employees in different sectors, 10% (4 people) were homemakers and 34% labor (14 people) of them belonged to labor class.

Age	Frequency
6	8
7-11	25
12-14	8

Table 2: Age vs Frequency

Figure 6: Age vs Frequency bar graph

Among the 41 children, 19.51% (8 children) had deciduous (primary) dentition, that is, 6 years. 60.98% (25 children) had mixed dentition that is 7-11 years and 19.51% (8 children) had permanent dentition that is, 12-14 years (shown in Table and Figure)

Figure 7: Responses filled by parents in Questionnaire

Above figure shows the responses of parents of all 41 children who were part of the study. Blue bar denotes a positive response to the corresponding question and the red bar denotes a negative response of parents. On x-axis are the questions in the questionnaire used for this study and on y-axis is the number of parents of the children that is, 41.

Categories	Mean	Standard Deviation	Frequency
Business	4.22	3.23	9
Employee	3.78	3.21	14
Homemaker	7	3.16	4
Labor	3.35	2.97	14

Table 3: Category-wise summary statistics of DMFT

Figure 8: Summary statistics of DMFT in relation with occupation of parents

Results

For the assessment of parental consent towards their child's oral health, a total of 50 questionnaires were distributed to the parents reporting in the department. Out of them, 9 questionnaire sheets were excluded for the study due to incomplete responses. The data sheet was made as per the requirement from 41 questionnaire sheets and subjected to statistical analysis.

As per the requirement of statistical analysis the table of occupation of parents was collapsed by merging similar occupations into 4 different categories that is, Business, employees, homemakers and labors. Significant association was observed between occupation of respondents and their responses in some questions. However, it has been observed that there is no relation of occupation and child's oral health concern in parents. This needs more emphasis on creating awareness between parents for the oral health of the child.

The correlation of mean DMFT scores across the 4 categories of occupation of the parents who have taken part in study were found almost comparable with non-significant p value ($p=0.2432$) from one way ANOVA Test.

The results clearly indicate that there is no correlation of mean DMFT scores with the parent's occupation. The parental concern is purely based upon the knowledge of child's oral health.

DISCUSSION

The study results showed that there is no correlation of mean DMFT scores with the parent's occupation. This hospital-based cross-sectional study was conducted in Nagpur district from August 2022 to September 2022 to assess parental awareness of their child's oral health. This study showed that 51.21% of parents felt the need to visit dentist only when they had caries or felt some kind of pain, which is similar to the study performed in Brazil.⁹

About 60.97% of parents did not feel the need to treat asymptomatic caries. A study performed by Azevedo MS et al. a high percentage of mothers neglected the importance of preserving primary dentition as they saw deciduous teeth as temporary and would be eventually replaced, which contradicted the findings of Salim Alsharif et al.¹³, who stated that parents believe that deciduous teeth are essential. This shows us that there is lack of awareness among the parents about the importance of primary teeth. If the caries affecting the primary teeth are not treated, then there is increased risk of caries affecting the permanent teeth, which reduces the self-esteem of the individual. The consumption of sugary foods and unhealthy snacks is very high nowadays, which causes pain and severe tooth decay and ultimately tooth loss and the parents have limited knowledge about the dietary causation of caries as showed in the study performed by Hoefl, K.S. et al.¹⁴

Oral health plays a very important role in one's life. Tooth brushing habits of child if monitored daily can reduce the risk of caries development. Dental examination started in the first year of life is an excellent method to make parents' attention directed to the future oral health of their children.¹⁵ Parents are the role-models for their children, and the habits adopted during childhood when the child is totally dependent on the mother are powerful means of establishing a novel behavior in children, such as that of tooth brushing.¹⁶

This study found that there was no statistically significant relationship between DMFT scores and parent's occupation. The results that I expected were that if the parent has good socioeconomic status than the child would have less caries and would have low DMFT score and that the parent would be aware about his/her child's oral health and vice versa as showed in study performed by S. Shaghaghian et al.³ Fernanda Alves de Lima Della Libera Trindade et al.⁹, Costa JRO et al.¹⁷, Okada M. et al.¹⁸, Sankeshwari RM et al.¹⁹ and Abiola Adeniyi et al.²⁰ Manchanda et al. had demonstrated that educating mothers in oral health led to a reduction of dental caries development in children.²¹ In my opinion, urban population today have greater access to processed and packaged foods high in sugar. As a result, children from high socioeconomic status families consume more of these foods, while those from low socioeconomic status families, who cannot afford such items, consume them less frequently or do not consume them at all.

Although there was no relation between the DMFT score and parents occupation, lack of awareness about the oral health and hygiene practices was seen amongst the parents. Many parents did not know the timing of the first dental visit. Therefore, there is a need to promote the educational programs for oral health in schools which involves the parents, teachers, guardians, caregivers, etc. However, before conducting or implementing any educational programs, surveys should be conducted to assess the parental knowledge about oral health so that there is understanding of where exactly they are lacking, and then the programs can be made according to that.

However, the sample size in my study was less which does not give accurate results and therefore, this constitutes a limitation of the study. So, further research is advised in this field to better understand whether the parent's occupation is more favorable in causation of caries. Another thing is that this study did not take the feeding practices of parents in consideration which also plays an important role in causation of caries, so this can also be explored in the upcoming researches.

CONCLUSION

Oral health plays a significant role in overall physical and mental growth of the child. Dental caries is the common oral disease in children. Parents usually ignore the dental caries in deciduous dentition, as they will exfoliate. This is due to lack of knowledge regarding oral diseases and their consequences in children. In this study, we have come across the conclusion that the parents have less concern towards their child's oral health considering their caries index. Thus, there is need of imparting knowledge through various awareness programs or by the means of other social media resources to the parents so that prevention will help in avoiding the consequences of oral diseases in children, thereby promoting overall better physical and mental growth in children.

SUMMARY

1. Despite various advancements in the field of dentistry, the knowledge and awareness about proper oral hygiene measures, practices and prevention is still low in parents.
2. There is lack of awareness among the parents about child's first dental visit.
3. Parents feel that visit to dentist should be given only if there is pain or discomfort to the child.
4. 51.21% of parents feel that regular dental check-up is not necessary.
5. 68.29% parents were not aware about the eruption and exfoliation stages of teeth.
6. Despite the parents knowing the importance of brushing teeth twice daily, only 29.26% of children reported brushing their teeth twice daily.
7. All these points suggest that there is a dire need for oral health awareness among the parents to ensure good oral health in children.

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